

NOTES

Fuoro Complexes of Hexavalent Uranium. Part-X. Complexes of Dioxouranium(VI) Containing Fluoride and Propionate

M. C. CHAKRAVORTI and (Miss) MANJU CHOWDHURY

Department of Chemistry,
Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur-721 302

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AMONG the carboxylato complexes of UO_2^{2+} the acetato and oxalato complexes have been thoroughly studied. Comparatively, the propionato ($C_2H_5COO^-$) complexes have received very little attention. $UO_2(C_2H_5COO)_2$ and a few compounds of the ion $[UO_2(C_2H_5COO)_3]^-$ have been prepared¹⁻¹⁵. The optical properties and thermal behaviour of the complexes have been studied. No mixed ligand complex of UO_2^{2+} containing propionato and other ligand has been prepared. In continuation to our studies on the mixed ligand complexes of UO_2^{2+} containing fluoride and acetate¹⁶ or oxalate¹⁷, we report in this communication the preparation and characterisation of propionatofluoro complexes of UO_2^{2+} .

Experimental

Uranyl nitrate, hydrogen peroxide, hydrofluoric acid (40%) and propionic acid used were of AnalaR (B.D.H.) or G.R. (E. Merck) quality. Preparation of the acid, $H[UO_2F_3].H_2O$ starting from $UO_2(NO_3)_2.6H_2O$ has been described in our earlier publications^{18,19}. Uranyl fluoride was prepared by heating $H[UO_2F_3].H_2O$ in a platinum crucible at 150° to a constant weight. Potassium propionate was prepared by neutralising propionic acid with potassium hydroxide followed by complete evaporation and drying in a desiccator over caustic soda. A solution of ammonium propionate was prepared by neutralising propionic acid with ammonium hydroxide and reducing the volume on the water-bath avoiding complete evaporation.

Analyses: Methods of analysis of uranium, potassium and fluorine were described in our previous papers^{17,18}. Uranium content of the compounds not containing potassium was also determined by igniting the compounds and weighing as U_3O_8 . Nitrogen was analysed by Dumas' method. Total fluoride and propionate content was determined by passing the salt solution through a column of cation exchange resin (Dowex 50-X8; A.R., J.T. Baker Chemical Co., Phillipsberg) in hydrogen form and titrating the effluent with standard alkali solution using phenolphthalein as indicator.

Physical measurements: Thermogravimetric analysis was done using a manual thermobalance. About 100 mg of the sample was heated at a rate of 2° per min. The conductivity measurements were made with a Systronics 303 direct reading conductivity meter using a polythene-body conductivity cell. Ir spectra were recorded in KBr pellets using a Perkin-Elmer 598 spectrophotometer in the range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} .

Preparation of complexes:

$NH_4[(UO_2)_2F_4(C_2H_5COO)]$, $NH_4[UO_2F_2(C_2H_5COO)]$ and $(NH_4)_2[UO_2F_2(C_2H_5COO)_2]$: A concentrated solution of UO_2F_2 (1.0 g) was mixed with concentrated solutions of ammonium propionate in the mole ratio of 1:1, 1:3 and 1:10, respectively with constant stirring. The crystalline solids separated after 5 min. The yields were 0.3, 0.6 and 0.8 g, respectively.

$K[UO_2F_2(C_2H_5COO)]$ and $K_2[UO_2F_2(C_2H_5COO)_2]$: These were prepared by a method similar to the above replacing ammonium propionate with appropriate amounts of potassium propionate in the UO_2F_2 : potassium propionate ratio of 1:1 and 1:3, respectively. Crystals of the compounds appeared immediately on stirring. The yields were 0.9 and 1.1 g, respectively. Crystallisation of UO_2F_2 and potassium propionate solutions in 1:10 mole ratio gave $K_2[UO_2F_2(C_2H_5COO)_2]$.

$NH_4[(UO_2)_2F_3(C_2H_5COO)_2]$ and $(NH_4)_2[(UO_2)_2F_3(C_2H_5COO)_4]$: These were prepared by slow evaporation of concentrated solutions of $NH_4[UO_2F_3(C_2H_5COO)]$ and $(NH_4)_2[UO_2F_3(C_2H_5COO)_2]$, respectively in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid. Starting with 1.0 g of the parent compounds the yields were about 0.3 g.

$(UO_2)_2F_3(C_2H_5COO)$: The compound was obtained by heating $(NH_4)_2[(UO_2)_2F_3(C_2H_5COO)_2]$ and $NH_4[(UO_2)_2F_3(C_2H_5COO)_2]$ at 150-160° to constant weight.

All the compounds, except the last one, were dried by pressing between folds of filter paper and then keeping in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid. The analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The compounds are yellow crystalline substances stable in air and soluble in water. The salts $K[UO_2F_2(C_2H_5COO)]$ and $NH_4[(UO_2)_2F_4(C_2H_5COO)]$ can be recrystallised unchanged from water. Recrystallisation of $K_2[UO_2F_2(C_2H_5COO)_2]$ from water gave $K[UO_2(C_2H_5COO)_2]$. Recrystallisation

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Total anion per U atom*	Molecular conductance** at 25° Ω ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹ cm ²
	U	F	Alkali metal or N		
K ₂ [UO ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO) ₂]	44.7 (44.7)	7.2 (7.1)	14.8 (14.7)	3.98 (4.0)	248
K[UO ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO)]	56.0 (56.6)	8.9 (9.0)	9.5 (9.3)	8.02 (8.0)	187
NH ₄ [UO ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO)]	60.3 (59.7)	9.6 (9.5)	9.4 (8.5)	2.98 (8.0)	187
(NH ₄) ₂ [UO ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO) ₂]	48.6 (48.6)	7.7 (7.8)	5.5 (5.7)	3.99 (4.0)	218
NH ₄ [(UO ₂) ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO)]	87.3 (87.8)	10.8 (10.8)	2.1 (2.0)	2.45 (2.5)	149
(NH ₄) ₂ [(UO ₂) ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO) ₂]	50.4 (50.5)	5.9 (6.0)	4.4 (4.5)	3.48 (3.5)	320
NH ₄ [(UO ₂) ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO) ₂]	62.7 (62.5)	7.4 (7.5)		2.50 (2.5)	196
(UO ₂) ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO)	70.6 (71.0)	8.8 (8.5)		1.99 (2.0)	116

* Total fluoride and propionate, calculated values in parenthesis.
** 1 × 10⁻³ M aqueous solution.

TABLE 2—TG DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Decomposition product	Temp. range of decomposition °C
(NH ₄) ₂ [UO ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO) ₂]	UO ₂ F ₂	70-880
NH ₄ [UO ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO)]	U ₂ O ₇	480-550
NH ₄ [(UO ₂) ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO)]	UO ₂ F ₂	70-340
	U ₂ O ₇	470-560
	UO ₂ F ₂	180-360
	U ₂ O ₇	460-540
NH ₄ [(UO ₂) ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO) ₂]	(UO ₂) ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO) ₂	70-200
	U ₂ O ₇	290-510
(NH ₄) ₂ [(UO ₂) ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO) ₂]	(UO ₂) ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO) ₂	70-200
	U ₂ O ₇	280-520

TABLE 3—IR SPECTRAL BANDS OF COMPLEXES (ν, cm⁻¹)

Compd.	ν(UO ₂) + ν(C-O)	ν _{as} (COO)	ν _s (COO) + δ(OH ₂)
K ₂ [UO ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO) ₂]	985 vs, 900 vs, 865 vs	1600 vs	1490 vs, 1460 vs, 1395 sh, 1305 s
K[UO ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO)]	985 vs, 900 vs, 865 w	1620 s, 1560 s	1490 vs, 1460 vs, 1400 m, 1305 s
NH ₄ [UO ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO)]	985 s, 900 s, 860 m	1640 s, 1540 s	1490 s, 1460 s, *1420 s, 1305 s
(NH ₄) ₂ [UO ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO) ₂]	985 s, 900 s	1560 vs	*1460 vs, 1305 s
(NH ₄)[(UO ₂) ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO)]	920 vs, 865 w	1640 s	*1420 s
(NH ₄) ₂ [(UO ₂) ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO) ₂]	985 vs, 900 vs	1540 vs	1460 vs, *1400 vs, 1305 vs
NH ₄ [(UO ₂) ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO) ₂]	985 s, 865 w	1620 s	1450 sh, *1420 s
(UO ₂) ₂ F ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ .COO)	930 vs, 850 m	1615 s	1395 vs
U(C ₂ H ₅ .COO) ₄ **	905 s	1570 s, 1510 s	1410 s, 1380 s

* Overlapped with ν₄ of NH₄⁺.

** For comparison (J. Selbin, M. Schober and J. D. Ortega, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, 28, 1985).

of (NH₄)₂[UO₂F₂(C₂H₅.COO)₂] and NH₄[UO₂F₂(C₂H₅.COO)] from water yielded the compounds (NH₄)₂[(UO₂)₂F₂(C₂H₅.COO)₂] and NH₄[(UO₂)₂F₂(C₂H₅.COO)₂], respectively. The molecular conductivity of the dilute solutions of all the potassium and ammonium salts except NH₄[(UO₂)₂F₂(C₂H₅.COO)₂] are almost within the expected range (Table 1) for the corresponding type of electrolyte. The compound (UO₂)₂F₂(C₂H₅.COO) dissociates completely in aqueous solution.

The thermogravimetric curves of the five ammonium salts were recorded upto 600°. The results of the thermal decomposition are given in Table 2. The TG curves of NH₄[(UO₂)₂F₂(C₂H₅.COO)₂] and (NH₄)₂[(UO₂)₂F₂(C₂H₅.COO)₂] gave horizontals stretching between 200-270° corresponding to the formation of (UO₂)₂F₂(C₂H₅.COO) which has been isolated.

The ir spectral band positions of the complexes are recorded in Table 3. All the complexes show

the presence of $\delta(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ band at $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (due to absorbed water from KBr). The band at $\sim 1540\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is tentatively assigned as $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ band. In sodium propionate²⁰ this band appears at 1540 cm^{-1} . This suggests that the propionate is present as a bidentate group, since in unidentate coordination this band is likely to be shifted to higher frequency²¹. The assignment of $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ in the complexes is rather difficult because of the appearance of $\delta(\text{CH}_3)$ or $\delta(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)$ bands and also NH_4^+ bands (in the ammonium salts) at $\sim 1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In the complexes the bands between 1490 and 146 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned as the $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ bands. The separation between $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ bands thus comes to about 100 cm^{-1} , which suggests that propionate is present as bidentate²¹ group. However, in the complexes containing UO_2^{2+} and carboxylate ion in the ratio 2:1, e.g. $\text{NH}_4[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COO})]$ and $(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COO})$, the carboxylate group may be present as a bridging group. It is interesting to note that in these two complexes the separation between $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ is larger. That $\text{NH}_4[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COO})]$ is thermally more stable than the other ammonium compounds (begins to decompose from 180°), supports the above viewpoint. The presence of fluoride bridging in the complexes cannot, however, be ruled out.

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Cyanato, Thiocyanato and Selenocyanato Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Zinc(II)

B. DAS* and P. C. ROY

Department of Chemistry, Government College,
Bourkela-769 004Manuscript received 5 March 1984, revised 12 October 1984,
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THE present communication reports the preparation and characterisation of some hexacoordinated mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) and zinc(II) pseudohalides, like cyanate, thiocyanate and selenocyanate with diamine ligands, i.e. propylenediamine (PDA), diethylenediamine (DDA) and *o*-phenylenediamine. The complexes were characterised by elemental analysis, molar conductance, infrared and electronic spectral data.

Experimental

Complexes were prepared by reacting an ethanolic solution of cobalt(II) and zinc(II) cyanate, thiocyanate and selenocyanate with appropriate ligands in stoichiometric ratios. The complexes were separated on standing and in some cases were obtained through refluxing the mixture for a few hours. All the compounds were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Analysis, conductance and magnetic susceptibility data are reported in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data indicate 1:2 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry for the complexes. The complexes melt or decompose above 200° . All the complexes are soluble in dimethylformamide in which molar conductance value was measured. They were found to be non-electrolytes as indicated by their low λ_M value (Table 1), hence all the anions are bonded to the metal ion. All the cobalt complexes under discussion are spin-free with magnetic moments ranging between 4.87 and 5.2 B.M. indicating the presence of three unpaired electrons. The magnetic moment values indicate that the complexes have octahedral geometry around the metal ion¹.

The infrared absorption attributed to $\nu_{\text{C}\equiv\text{N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$ for the complexes exhibit strong band at 2205-2225 and bands of medium and wide intensity at $1300-1315\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. These bands indicate that in cyanato complexes, the cyanate is bonded to metal through nitrogen atom^{2,3}. The bands occurring at $2050-2080$ and $800-830\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the case of thiocyanate complexes indicate that thiocyanate groups are

* Present Address: Regional Research Laboratory,
Bhubaneswar-751 013.